

Table 1 Rows group wild Atlantic salmon female growth-related parameters (length (cm) and weight (Kg), ovarian fluid (OF) pH, conductivity (mS cm^{-1}), density (g/cm^3), volume (mL; per centimetre, per kilogram and per 10 grams of eggs) and apparent viscosity values at 10, 50, 100 and 500 $\text{rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ ($\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$). In columns, left to right values are expressed as means \pm standard deviations (SD), range (min-max), and coefficient of variation (CV%) among females ($n=11$).

	Mean \pm SD	Range (Min-Max)	CV (%)
Fish length (cm)	54.55 \pm 5.714	40.90 - 74.20	10%
Fish weight (Kg)	1.556 \pm 0.530	0.57 - 3.54	34%
OF volume (ml) per cm of fish	1.06 \pm 0.54	0.23 - 2.20	51%
OF volume (ml) per Kg of fish	37.78 \pm 19.05	7.97 - 64.98	50%
OF volume (ml) per 10 gr of eggs	2.38 \pm 1.32	0.53 - 4.41	55%
OF pH	8.264 \pm 0.117	8.010 - 8.57	1%
OF conductivity ($\text{mS} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$)	14.19 \pm 0.674	11.77 - 15.19	5%
OF density ($\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$)	0.993 \pm 0.091	0.8220- 1.530	9%
OF apparent viscosity ($\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$) at 10 $\text{rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	0.012 \pm 0.006	0.006 - 0.029	57%
OF apparent viscosity ($\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$) at 50 $\text{rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	0.004 \pm 0.001	0.002 - 0.008	40%
OF apparent viscosity ($\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$) at 100 $\text{rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	0.003 \pm 0.001	0.002 - 0.005	32%
OF apparent viscosity ($\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$) at 500 $\text{rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	0.002 \pm 0.000	0.001 - 0.003	17%

Figure 1 Apparent viscosity obtained from the steady shear flow curves (η) of Atlantic salmon ovarian fluid samples ($n= 11$, in grey) and water controls in blue, plotted versus shear rate (s^{-1}) on a log-log scale. Grey symbols and dotted lines represent individual ovarian fluid means across 3 replicates per female and their fitted equations respectively, while the red and blue symbols and the continuous lines represent the mean across all ovarian fluid samples (red) and water controls (blue). The symbols σ_{00} and η_{∞} are respectively the Yield stress and the apparent viscosity at high shear rates obtained from the fitting

to the Herschel-Bulkley equation; η_{water} instead represents the average apparent viscosity value of water within the analysed shear rates (mean \pm SD)

Figure 2. (A) Storage modulus (G'), loss modulus (G'') and complex viscosity (η^*) of Atlantic salmon ovarian fluids ($n=11$), to describe the relation between the viscous and elastic components of the fluid at increasing angular frequencies ($0 < \Omega < 500 \text{ rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$). Data are presented as means \pm SD, continuous lines for η^* represent individual ovarian fluid means across three replicates for each female. **(B)** Loss factor ($\tan \delta = G''/G'$) of Atlantic salmon ovarian fluids (mean \pm SD) plotted versus frequency ($\text{rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, Hz for reference), where $\tan \delta = 100$ for a liquid material with a pure viscous behaviour and $\tan \delta = 0.01$ for a solid material with an ideally elastic behaviour. Vertical dotted lines from left to right represent a reference baseline at 1 Hz and Atlantic salmon average sperm tail beat frequencies in Hz from Dzievulska et al., 2011a, b. Graph is plotted on log-log scale.

Figure 3 Comparison between the steady state and the dynamic properties of Atlantic salmon ovarian fluid (OF). Apparent viscosity obtained from the steady shear flow curves (η_a) of Atlantic salmon ovarian fluid (OF) samples ($N= 11$, red) and complex viscosity (η^*) of Atlantic salmon ovarian fluids ($n= 11$, blue) plotted versus shear rate (s^{-1}). Values are presented as mean \pm SD (grey vertical bars). Graph is plotted on log-log axes.